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SUSINCHAIN (SUStainable INsect CHAIN): Introduction to the project

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The aim of the SUSINCHAIN project is to overcome the remaining barriers for increasing the economic viability of the insect value chain and opening markets. This will be done by combining forces in a comprehensive multi-actor consortium with 18 industry partners and 17 academic partners. SUSINCHAIN considers the entire insect value chain from farm (insect rearing) to fork (insect consumption) based on black soldier fly, housefly, mealworm and crickets. The SUSINCHAIN concept is based on performing all activities needed (innovations, testing, demonstrating, sharing knowledge) to overcome the most important hurdles for scaling up the European insect value chain. Practical experience of consortium industry partners in addressing supply-side barriers as well as related risk management strategies will be evaluated and best practices will be elaborated by the use of living labs. Insect rearing innovations will be focused on organic side streams of vegetable origin that cannot be used directly as animal feed. For improving economic viability, possibilities for marketing of rearing by-products will be evaluated and strategies to avoid insect diseases will be developed. Transport, storage and processing technologies for insects will be optimised and demonstrated at large scale. Microwave and Radio Frequency drying, High Moisture Extrusion and protein recovery from fresh larvae by using enzymatic pre-treatment combined with continuous tricanter centrifugation will be validated and demonstrated. Controlled atmosphere packaging and cold atmosphere preservation for storage and transport of living insects will also be tested. The digestibility of insect meals produced by different processing methods will be assessed and insect meals will be included in feed formulae for large-scale level commercial diets to test optimal inclusion levels to maintain or increase livestock performance and health. Insect based food products will be designed and developed suitable for the domestic preparation of regular dinner meals. The microbiological, chemical and allergenic safety of insects and derived products will be addressed along the entire chain. Hygiene codes, HACCP protocols, and guidelines for safe insect production will be created and distributed among the supply chain actors. Furthermore, a decision support system will be developed to ensure the sustainable growth of the insect value chain in Europe, in addition to the stakeholder's platform provided within the context of the project in order to connect and receive valuable inputs from the relevant actors.